

Advances in Thermodynamics of Amino Acid Solutions

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The solubility of amino acids have been compiled at different temperatures to understand the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids in going from water to various solvent systems and interpreted in terms of solute-solvent interactions and structural changes of the amino acids in solvent mixture. A variety of solubility determination methods have been presented systematically. The order of solubility seems to be a function of specific solute-solvent interactions with non-polar portions of the amino acid molecules. The paper presents a review of advancements in thermodynamic behaviour of amino acids in various solvent (pure/mixed) systems.

Amino acids are found in living organisms in both their free forms and bound by amide linkages in peptides and proteins. Solvents have profound effect on the solubility of amino acids. Solubility studies of amino acids in different solvent systems are of much importance because of suitable conditions for their separation and purification can be achieved. Solubility data may also provide sufficient insight into the various structural changes responsible for dissolution and also on the nature of solute-solvent interactions. It has been reported that in pure solvent systems the solubility of certain amino acids was dominated by the α -aminocarboxylic acid group, thus producing a high solubility in water and a substantially lower solubility in the alcohols. If the attraction that causes the solubility of the amino acid dipoles is defined as being due to the highly polar water molecules interacting with the charged portion of the amino acid, and the semipolar solvents are assumed to have too little polarity to interact with the charged portion of the amino acids, then it would be expected that the addition of a semipolar liquid to the polar aqueous solvent would be reflected by a proportionate decrease in the solubility of the amino acids.

Much efforts have been made to obtain the solubility data of amino acids and related compounds in a number of pure and mixed solvents, especially in those containing well known protein denaturants, such as urea and guanidine hydrochloride. Most of these studies were made with an aim to determine the corresponding properties of proteins using model compound additive approach¹. As is now known that model compound approach is no longer true because of the cooperative nature of protein folding², people get interested in solubility of these compounds to know the basis of intermolecular forces between solute and solvent molecules. For instance, why at any specified pressure and temperature α -aminobutyric acid is more soluble in water than β -alanine, although the former has a larger hydrophobic chain and why the amino acids having carboxyl groups (aspartic and glutamic acids) or hydroxyl groups (tyrosine) as side-chains are least soluble among the

primary protein amino acids and why those containing amino or imino groups (lysine and proline) are most soluble? All the amino acids are more soluble in glacial acetic acid than water, rendering the former a useful component of solvent systems for paper and thin layer chromatography.

The solubility data of amino acids under various conditions are available of Hutchens³ even that upto 1976 and few comparative studies upto 1971 by Nozaki and Tanford⁴⁻⁷, it is considered worth to review the subject and make a readily available compiled informations useful for further investigations, with a brief comments on the experimental procedures and relative nature of some mixed solvents.

Retrospective

To give a bird's eye-view of the solubility studies, a chart (Table 1) has been prepared which shows a number of vacancies, that among twenty primary amino acids, seven, namely, asparagine, arginine, glutamine, proline, cysteine, isoleucine and lysine have not been studied well, and among the studied, only glycine is extensively reported. Further, from the literature survey, it was observed that the contribution of ω -amino acids toward solubility data is almost negligible⁸.

In most of the studies the reported data are only free energy of transfer from one solvent to another, essentially from mixed solvents to water. In very few studies the raw solubility data is also reported. As pH of the solvent has profound effect on the solubility of zwitterionic amino acids, it is also of interest to note that in only one study⁹ among many reported in Table 1, the pH of the saturated amino acids solution either in mixed or in water is considered to be important. From the pH measurements for the various amino acids in isopropanol-water mixtures, Dey *et al.*⁹, observed that K_1 for the reaction,

increases with alcohol concentration while K_2 remains almost constant.

TABLE 1—REPRESENTATIVE LIST OF THE STUDIES MADE ON SOLUBILITY OF AMINO ACIDS

Temp. °C	Cosolute in water	Data reported	Methods of measurement	Ref.
	Alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, histidine, leucine, phenylalanine, serine and valine			
15, 20	Methanol	$S, \Delta G_t$	Spectrophotometric	8, 11
	Alanine, glycine and valine			
15, 25, 35	Na_2SO_4	S	Formal titration, dry weight	8, 15
	Glycine			
15, 20, 25, 30, 35	Urea, glycerol, NaNO_3	ΔG_t	Formal titration	16
	Alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, glutamic acid, histidine and methionine			
20, 25, 29.8	Na_2SO_4 , CuCl	ΔG_t	Density	15
	Alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, glutamic acid, histidine, leucine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan and tyrosine			
25 1	Urea, CuCl , ethylene glycol	S	Optical rotation	4-6
	Aspartic acid, glycine, glutamic acid, histidine, leucine, phenylalanine, tryptophan and tyrosine			
25.1	Ethanol, dioxide	S	Dry-weight	7
	Alanine, glycine, leucine, phenylalanine and tyrosine			
25	Urea	ΔG_t	Not reported	17
	Alanine, glycine, leucine, phenylalanine, tryptophan and valine			
25	Polyols ^a	S	Dry-weight, Kjeldahl	14
	Alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, histidine, leucine, phenylalanine, serine and valine			
25	Alcohols ^b	$S, \Delta G_t$	Spectrophotometric, dry weight	8, 10-13

^aAlcohols are methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, isopropanol and t-butanol.

^bPolyols are methanol, glycerol, erythritol, xylitol, sorbitol and inositol.

It is to be noted that RH_2^+ and R^- can be obtained from RH^\pm or neutral amino acid by the addition of acid or alkali but since the concentration of zwitterion is negligibly small (less than 0.1% even in high percentages of alcohol), we can consider the above reactions to correctly represent the dissociation equilibrium. Thus, the amino acids in water are present as equilibrium of zwitterion and ions (cation and anion, where cation predominates) with almost no traces of neutral form. The decrease in solubility with increasing organic solvent suggests that there is little conversion to neutral form; rather due to the increase in the basic character of the organic solvent mixtures, the amino acid would be converted into anion. The amino acid in mixed solvent would thus be an equilibrium mixture of zwitterion and anion (predominantly).

Methods of measurement

A number of methods (Table 1) have been identified for the solubility determination of amino acids in pure and mixed solvents. These are : dry weight analysis Kjeldahl, formal titration, spectrophotometric, optical rotation and

density measurements. The selection of an appropriate method depends predominately on the nature of solvent and little on solute.

Dry-weight technique is used when the solvent is volatile and that too not containing any nonvolatile solute such as guanidine hydrochloride, urea or alkali halides, etc.

Spectrophotometric determination involves the complexation of amino acid with ninhydrin to form a coloured complex^{18,19} and the measured optical density is extrapolated on the calibration curve. Since the complexation is quantitative and the optical density versus concentration is a linear function, the method is reasonably accurate and can be used for almost all the amino acids. However, tyrosine has its own absorbance at 275 nm, it can be determined without any complexation.

Optical rotation¹⁷ is still another method which can be used for the quantitative estimation of optically active amino acids, except glycine, but the method has not been used widely. In the recent studies^{8,16}, formal-titration was used to estimate the dissolved amino acid. In such a method freshly neutralised formaldehyde solution is added to the solution to be titrated, within 2-3 days equilibrium is attained and the solution is titrated with standard alkali using phenolphthalein indicator. Talukdar *et al.*¹⁶ reported an error of $\pm 1\%$ in solubility data obtained by this method.

There is still another method which is not used extensively is density measurements¹⁵. The method is somewhat similar to the spectrophotometric determination, a calibration curve is drawn and the density of experimental solution is extrapolated to know the concentration.

On the basis of the fundamentals and various results, if a comparison is made between these methods, we would like to comment that the density and dry-weight methods are more reliable and the formal titration is the least one. Even after a critical survey of literature, we ourselves were unable to find the theory of formal titration and the magnitude of equilibrium constant so as to know, why it took 2-3 days to attain the equilibrium and how complete is the complexation of formaldehyde with amino acid?

Discussion

The amino acids are characterised by the presence of hydrophilic centres (CO_2^- , NH_3^+) and hydrophobic centre (R) leading to two different types of hydration. Thus, both hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions compete for water structure organisation. The addition of amino acid to water leads to the rupture of the tetrahedral structure of water. When two non-polar regions (of amino acids) come close together, these regions are shielded to a greater extent from interaction with water molecules leading to the collapse of some of the quasi-crystalline water structure and a gain in entropy. The addition of amino acid to solvent also leads to a structural changes as would be apparent from the large positive entropy values. Since the nature of the reacting groups is the same for all the amino acids, the changes in thermodynamic properties can be attributed to specific solvation effects and hydrophobic effects.

Specific solvation effects are dependent mainly on the composition of the solvent mixture, being greatest for strongly solvated amino acid, the hydrophobic effect on the other hand increase with the size of the solute molecules and is maximum where maximum enhancement of the water structure occurs, i.e. in the region of 0.2 to 0.3% mole fraction of solvent. The specific solvation effect and the hydrophobic effect act in the opposite directions. The hydrophobic effect increases with the increase in the size of the solute and shifts the point of maximum structure-formation towards the media richer in water.

However, it is expected that the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids²⁰⁻²⁴ from water to various solvent mixtures will give better idea regarding structural and interaction parts of the solvents. The solubility properties of the amino acids studied were found to be dominated by the α -aminocarboxylic acid portion of the molecule but also depended to some extent on the non-polar portion of the molecule and its interaction with each specific solvent system. These interactions give rise to a rank order of solubility which was characteristic of the specific amino acid rather than the decreasing polarity of the solvent system.

Since there is no regularity in the structure of primary amino acids, all of these are structurally very different, unlike ω -amino acids, comparison of the solubility data under similar conditions is rather difficult. Even if it were possible the conclusions will still be hampered by two other influencing factors : (i) different crystal forms of amino acids and their relative crystal binding energy and (ii) the activity coefficient of these in saturated solutions. The activity coefficient (γ) varies greatly with the nature of the amino acid in water, so it is worth to report and discuss the free energy of transfer from water to solvent under considering rather than the solubility data itself. The free energy transfer from water 'w' to solvent 's' is given by

$$\Delta G_t = RT \ln (N_{i,w}/N_{i,s}) + RT \ln (\gamma_{i,w}/\gamma_{i,s})$$

where, N_i is the mole fraction of solute 'i' in water or solvent 's' and γ_i is the respective activity coefficient⁴. Thus, the effect of solvent on the chemical potential of the solute at infinite dilution is contained entirely in the term ΔG_t . The term $RT \ln \gamma_i$ represents solely the effect of solute-solute interactions.

Activity coefficient values for most of the amino acids in water are available in literature²⁵⁻²⁷ but unfortunately these are not available in the solvents used for solubility measurements. For many of these solute solvents systems $\gamma_{i,s}$ values were only estimated by taking it at saturation in a mixed solvent to be equal to $\gamma_{i,w}$ at the same solute concentration in water and multiplying $RT \ln (\gamma_{i,w}/\gamma_{i,s})$ by D_w/D_s , the respective dielectric constants⁴. For mixed solvents containing non-aqueous solvents like alcohols or polyols at their high concentration, $RT \ln (\gamma_{i,w}/\gamma_{i,s})$ is likely to represent an unimportant source of error and moreover the polyols do not greatly reduce the dielectric constant of

water over the normal range of concentration the term D_w/D_s can be taken as unity.

It can be fairly observed from Table 1 that aqueous polyhydric and monohydric alcohols including urea, guanidine hydrochloride and sodium sulphate are the extensively reported solvents. A good comparison of the data can be made for each of these series. Free energies of transfer from water to aqueous polyols and to aqueous aliphatic alcohols for some amino acids are clubbed in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. At a particular concentration of polyol in water and for a given amino acid²⁸⁻³¹ the free energy of transfer decrease sharply (Table 2) with the increase in molecular weight of the polyol, i.e. with the increase in number of hydroxyl groups on the polyol. The reverse is observed in the case of monohydric alcohols (Table 3), where the ΔG_t for an amino acid increases with the increase in hydrophobic chain or molecular weight of the alcohols. However, this behaviour can be understood on the basis of the different structural hydration characteristics of binary solvent systems. For the monohydric alcohols, the solvent becomes more structured with the increase in non-polar side-chain resulting in lesser entropy contribution, while for polyol solutions the structural order decreases with increase of polyol molecular weight³² due to increasing incompatibility of the higher homologous and thereby increasing the entropy. Effect of solvent structure around the solute molecules is also clearly evidenced by the en-

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER^a ΔG_t (cal mol⁻¹) OF AMINO ACIDS FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS POLYOL SOLUTIONS AT 25^o

Cosolute	Alcohol/ Water % w/v	ΔG_t				
		Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe
Ethylene glycol	30	275	305	—	145	60
	60	605	610	—	250	-60
	90	950	930	—	135	-165
Methanol ^b	16	341	314	260	190	160
	32	779	697	533	345	240
	48	1323	1155	796	428	251
	64	2082	1788	1153	603	361
Glycerol	10	38	56	70	47	21
	20	67	99	107	83	26
	30	136	166	145	121	38
	40	204	210	216	171	38
Xylitol ^c	7.6	3	11	28	9	4
	15.1	8	14	40	28	13
	22.7	12	27	56	49	16
	30.3	16	40	70	60	26
Sorbitol ^c	9.1	1	14	26	4	1
	18.2	0	19	47	19	5
	27.2	2	28	68	34	8
	36.3	11	56	101	63	11

^a ΔG_t values taken from Ref. 14 except for ethylene glycol which are from Ref. 5.

^b%w/v converted from % v/v.

^cw/v converted from molality.

TABLE 3—FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER^a ΔG_t (cal mol⁻¹) OF AMINO ACIDS FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS ALCOHOL SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Cosolute %, w/v	ΔG_t				
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe
	Methanol + Water				
8.0	27.3	56.4	44.8	53.3	37.3
34.4	591.3	877.3	730.1	679.9	1022.7
54.2	1805.9	1377.8	801.6	732.3	1145.7
87.5	2617.4	2819.2	4202.0	1959.2	1994.5
	Ethanol + Water				
8.0	41.5	63.4	79.6	63.8	58.7
16.0	86.1	142.5	126.3	151.5	491.4
34.4	628.7	913.2	801.6	710.8	1101.8
54.2	1824.9	1402.7	882.8	766.2	1331.4
87.5	2663.6	2942.1	4504.6	2043.3	2284.4
	iso-Propanol + Water				
8.0	96.5	122.7	93.2	81.8	80.9
16.0	128.8	210.7	146.0	168.2	506.7
34.4	726.4	951.4	832.7	732.3	1123.3
54.2	1942.7	1465.1	900.5	789.8	1363.4
87.5	3649.5	3159.9	4545.5	2141.3	2350.3
	t-Butanol + Water				
8.0	140.0	150.6	97.8	96.6	88.5
16.4	205.5	238.5	161.3	185.4	522.3
34.4	782.1	967.4	849.0	743.4	1145.7
54.2	2046.0	1493.9	928.0	814.5	1397.3
87.5	3980.8	3193.7	4612.6	2165.5	2386.1

^a ΔG_t values are taken from Ref. 13 except for t-butanol which is from Ref. 12.

enthalpy-entropy compensation diagnostic test³³. Lumry and Rajender³⁴ found that there is a linear correlation between the enthalpy and entropy changes involved in many process in water and that the linear relationship can be used as a diagnostic test for the participation of water in the process. The entropy of transfer of amino acids can be used as structural probe to understand the structural changes taking place in various solvent systems in presence of the amino acids. The solubility of the amino acids studied was at a maximum in water and was inversely related to the length of the non-polar portion of the molecule³⁵.

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